

Some people say that better institutions drive economic growth. Others claim that economic growth leads to better institutions. What is your opinion on the relationship between institutions and growth? In light of the relationship, what development policy would you recommend in low-income countries?

(ES30035: Coursework)

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One only needs to look at Haiti to see the importance of institutions on the social, economic and political fabric of a nation. Centuries of expropriation of the nation's resources before and after independence is widely attributed to the recent collapse of the nation (www.oecd-ilibrary.org, 2021).

However, when looking at institutions, growth, and the direction of causality between the two, it is paramount to define both. Institutions are the hardest to define, as they are an umbrella term that encompasses everything from rule of law, property rights, and The Beatles. This paper will follow North's (1974) definition of institutions, which are "a set of rules, compliance procedures, and moral and ethical behavioral norms designed to constrain the behavior of individuals in the interest of maximizing the wealth or utility of principles". This definition is convenient as it allows us to focus on political, economic and social institutions within the context of governance. Regarding the question, this paper will look at how institutions cause growth through two chains of causality, state capacity and institutional persistence, and then recommend redistribution as a policy through these two channels.

A key determinant of institutions, particularly political institutions, is state capacity. State capacity measures the ability of the political institutions to meet its policy goals, usually with respect to fiscal objectives and rule of law (Dincecco, M. and Wang, Y., 2022). Within state capacity, the main budget constraint preventing governments to enact or expand on their state capacity is revenue generated, usually from taxation. From these revenues, the state can invest in public goods like policing or a tax service to extend its ability to govern effectively. We are concerned with state capacity, as it is likely that investment in expanding state capacity (and hence institutional effectiveness) leads to better growth prospects for nations. Dincecco and Wang (2022) show in Figure 1 (see appendices) that fiscal capacity measured through average income tax share has a positive relationship with real GDP per capita. They explain that higher levels of revenue extraction by the state can be spent items such as the enforcement of property rights, fostering technological innovation, and advancing human capital.

Dincecco and Katz (2014) explain the potential causal relationship between changes in state capacity and economic growth. They explore this relationship through a panel regression, using the regression equation:

$$\Delta y_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^2 \beta_j \Delta E_{i,t-j} + \beta_3 \ln E_{i,t-3} + X'_{i,t-1} \beta_4 + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

This equation looks at lagged measures of annual state capacity growth, E_i , regressed against the real annual growth rate of GDP per capita in a nation, $\Delta y_{i,t}$. When regressed, the output shows that there is a "significant relationship between extractive capacity improvements and subsequent per capital GDP growth" (Dincecco, Katz, 2014), with the coefficient for extraction ranging from 0.11 to 0.15. This result is also historically backed. By the 1700s, England had already established a centralised revenue extractive political system that was relatively efficient in generating tax revenues. Compare this with France, which had an overly capable state that still operated under and absolute monarch, it is not surprising that per capita state revenues were 7.5 grams of gold for England and 3.71 for France (Dincecco, Katz 2014). Importantly, the paper also tests the relationship between state capacity and political transformations, in order to establish a chain of causality. They find that political transformations through fiscal centralisation and limited government does lead to greater tax extractive potential for a state. This then completes the causality chain, as seen in Figure 2, showing that through initial political change state capacity can increase, which increases investment by governments and hence GDP per capita rises.

However, as stipulated above, it is possible for a state to be too capable. A very capable state, coupled with an authoritarian regime, can be detrimental to economic growth. Government revenues from taxation – or more aggressive extraction methods – can be used to fund institutions that hinder welfare rather than improve it. An example of this was the collectivisation and reappropriation of grain from the peasant class by the USSR in the 1920s and 1930s, which led to a famine that decimated that led to the deaths of tens of millions (Conquest, 1986). To prevent this, there needs to be checks and balances in place to prevent the development of authoritative institutions. The most effective constraint is the establishment and supremacy of an elected legislative. By giving a freely elected parliament authority over state capacity, it is able to invest in public goods more effectively without compromising welfare (Dincecco, M. and Wang, Y., 2022). The Red Queen effect proposed by Acemoglu and Robinson (2020) highlights this phenomenon, and how societies are balancing on a tightrope between effective state capacity and totalitarianism.

A perfect example of a nation with effective state capacity to bolster growth is the success story of Mauritius after its independence from the British. Mauritius currently ranks 1st in Africa for its HDI at 0.802, classed as very high human development and comparable to Serbia, Thailand, or Malaysia. It also ranks in the top 3 African nations by GDP per capita, at \$10,216 (data.worldbank.org, n.d.). However, this has not always been the case. Mauritius was found by the Dutch East India Company in 1638, and when the British inherited it they transformed it into a sugar plantation rooted in African slave labour (Frankel, 2010). When the nation gained independence in 1968, it was at the precipice of a civil war given its incredibly diverse population of Hindu Indians, Muslims, Chinese, Africans, and French Creole. Why then was Mauritius able to be so successful while other African nations lagged behind?

Good institutions and efficient state capacity seem to be the consensus argument. Taxation was, and continues to be, a substantial component of government revenues. In fact, tax revenues in 1980 were larger on a nominal and % GDP basis compared with the early 2000s. Early on, Mauritius chose to keep rents on sugar plantations – their main export at the time – relatively modest. They could have let taxes run high for maximum extraction, and hence increase state capacity. However, the government understood that if it wanted to preserve the sugar industry, it would have to balance out taxation for state capacity and allowing the industry to invest and grow. Yao et al. (2005) exhibits the importance of institutions in Mauritius through a panel regression. They break down the determinants of growth between “inheritance variables” that are either fixed or endowed and “policy variables” that are based off institutional choices, and then compare the variables to Africa, fast growing countries, and other developing countries. These variables are then regressed with respect to economic growth. The results show that institutional quality is a large, positive contributor to economic growth compared to all other baselines. In this study, institutional quality is an indexed measure of protection against expropriation. Within Africa, the discrepancy between Mauritius and the average coefficient of African nations is particularly high at 0.75. The overall conclusion of this is that “institutional quality is likely to have been a significant factor in explaining Mauritius’s economic performance” (Yao et al., 2005).

Whilst looking at institutions within the context of developing nations is important, it is equally insightful to compare them to developed nations as that may help us explain the difference in institutions and growth paths. Predominantly, state capacity is not the only determinant that can explain institutional quality and development. Factor endowments of institutions by colonial governors, and the persistence and exacerbation of these institutions have had a significant and outsized impact on the quality of institutions – and hence economic growth. This can mainly be explained by the persistence of either extractive, unequal institutions, or inclusive ones. Extractive institutions are defined as institutions that are either not centralised and/or not pluralistic (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). If an institution is decentralised, it makes the task of accountability challenging which may benefit bad actors. Whilst a non-pluralistic institution is one controlled by a small, likeminded committee or by a single political party.

Institutional persistence is often cited as a lead determinant of growth path divergence between nations.

This can be seen in the discrepancy between the US and Latin America, both former European colonies but with vastly different growth and development trajectories. By analysing land policies, we can see how the implementation of different property right policies may have impacted institutions and growth. Land policy plays a large impact in the determination of institutions, as not only is land an asset and a source of taxation, but as a store of wealth it plays a role in power dynamics between individuals and groups (Sokoloff and Engerman, 2000). Looking at the US and Canada, land was not only abundant but the barriers to acquire land was relatively low as both the British and American governments promoted settlers to expand farther west. Compared to Latin America, land ownership was purposely concentrated amongst a smaller number of monopolists to keep production controlled, which led to a much larger inequality of output. In North America, low barriers to land led to a larger number of grain producers, which was much more equal in terms of production and wealth. Wealth and land ownership came with political clout, hence it is no surprise that unequal land regimes continued to persist in Latin America across generations. More surprisingly, unequal land policies spilled over into other forms of government, such as corporate law and industrial policy (Sokoloff and Engerman, 2000). Areas with greater land concentration had institutions that were more beneficial to the elite, sustaining these extractive institutions and widening the inequality gap. Although, it is important to ask – why do we care about inequality?

There is evidence that inequality is detrimental to economic growth, which allows us to establish a chain of causality between the persistence of extractive institutions and growth. Looking at democracies, uneven wealth distributions should lower growth. A panel regression by Alesina and Rodrik (1994) shows this, and they explain how workers would vote for excessively high taxes on capitalists that would offset any potential wage gains from redistribution. They also cover non-democratic populist economies, and how a similar albeit smaller effect is seen between inequality and growth.

We can also look at the importance of inequality through the lens of human capital. As stipulated above, institutions and policies built to benefit the elite will continue to do so as long as the elite are still in power. Sokoloff and Engerman (2000) stipulate that the preference for the provision of education by the US and Canada contributed to greater human capital formation compared to the Caribbean nations or Latin America, which were lagging in educational provision. This is significant as it is widely researched that human capital formation is a cornerstone to modern economic growth (Galor, 2012). From these conclusions, we can create another causality chain as seen in Figure 4. We have established that extractive institutions can persist, which develops into greater wealth inequality and human capital degradation that both lead to less economic growth.

We now investigate potential policy developing countries can employ given the positive causality between institutions and economic growth. Looking at the two chains of causality we have developed, wealth redistribution policies implemented by political institutions are likely to be the most effective. These policies would include taxes on capital, income or land for high percentile earners and redistributing towards the lower and middle class. Through the state capacity argument, we can concur that implementing a tax would be an increase in fiscal capacity, which we have proven can be invested in public goods and lead to growth. Greater taxation would improve the state's capacity to provide for public goods such as education, and improving human capital should benefit growth. This is similar to the Mauritius argument, as the island nation was effective in taxing its profitable sugar industry early on and used these revenues in strengthening/improving existing institutions. Also, the persistence of redistribution within Mauritius throughout its modern history kept state capacity effective, as opposed to a onetime policy implementation.

In addition, redistribution is the preferred policy when looking at unequal wealth and human capital distributions due to institutional persistence. Aghion, Caroli and García-Peñalosa (1999) argue that redistribution does have a positive effect on growth through improving equality. Not only is this seen through higher marginal tax rates, but through land distributions and education reform within developing nations. This is pivotal when considering that it may be easier for developing nations with weaker educational institutions to benefit from land outputs rather than solely focusing on human capital advancement, considering the relatively higher monetary and institutional barriers of entry needed for educational improvement.

However, this policy relies on an independent and strong democratic legislative body within the nation to enact these policies. The Red Queen effect mentioned above plays into effect here, as checks and balances are needed to prevent the state from being too capable and hence create/sustain extractive institutions. If political institutions are weak, an authoritarian ruler or the elite can overrule any equality-improving policies like redistribution if they believe it will lead to marginal losses in their wealth or power. Over time, as redistribution policies persist, any existing despot or elite should lose influence as the general electorate becomes wealthier through a narrowing inequality gap.

We have established two key chains of causalities that show that institutions cause economic growth. First, we looked at state capacity, and how if political institutions are capable of collecting taxation that it translates to sustainable economic growth, as long as the state isn't too capable and oversteps its prerogative. We also looked at institutional persistence, and how the establishment of poor institutions by colonial powers led to greater wealth and educational inequality, which also dampened growth. Despite this, the literature around this topic is vast and there is still no consensus agreement amongst scholars about whether institutions cause economic growth. Taking a page from Banerjee and Duflo (2014), they argue that in the presence of uncertainty regarding whether institutions are deterministically made or a factor of luck, we should assume these policies due lead to institutions. Similarly, given that it seems likely but still debated that institutions cause economic growth, we should pragmatically assume they do until a definite answer – if there is one – is found.

Word count: 2360

Appendices

Figure 1: Relationship between per capita GDP and state capacity

Figure 2: Chain of causality between political change and GDP per capita
(Period averages; in percent of GDP)

	1980/81– 1984/85	1985/86– 1989/90	1990/91– 1994/95	1995/96– 1999/00	2000/01– 2003/04
Total revenue and grants	21.6	22.8	21.3	19.7	19.5
Total revenue	21.1	22.2	21.1	19.5	19.2
Tax revenue	18.7	20.1	18.9	16.9	16.7
Nontax revenue	2.4	2.1	2.2	2.6	2.5
External grants	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.3
Total expenditure and net lending	30.2	24.9	23.8	24.5	25.3
Current expenditure	24.4	20.0	19.5	20.6	20.9
Capital expenditure and net lending	5.8	4.9	4.3	4.0	4.4
Overall balance after grants	-8.6	-2.1	-2.5	-4.9	-5.8
Primary balance	-2.8	2.2	0.7	-1.4	-1.8

Sources: Mauritian authorities and IMF staff estimates.

Figure 3

Figure 4: Chain of causality between extractive institutions and economic growth

References:

- Acemoglu, D. and Robinson, J.A. (2012). *Why nations fail: the origins of power, prosperity and poverty*. London: Profile Books.
- Acemoglu, D. and Robinson, J.A. (2020). *The narrow corridor : states, societies, and the fate of liberty*. New-York: Penguin Books.
- Aghion, P., Caroli, E. and García-Peñalosa, C. (1999). Inequality and Economic Growth: The Perspective of the New Growth Theories. *Journal of Economic Literature*, [online] 37(4), pp.1615–1660.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.37.4.1615>.
- Alesina, A. and Rodrik, D. (1994). Distributive Politics and Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, [online] 109(2), pp.465–490. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2118470>.
- Conquest, R. (1986). *Harvest of sorrow*. Oxford University Press.
- data.worldbank.org. (n.d.). *Mauritius | Data*. [online] Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/country/MU>.
- Dincecco, M. and Katz, G. (2014). State Capacity and Long-Run Economic Performance. *The Economic Journal*, 126(590), pp.189–218. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/eoj.12161>.
- Dincecco, M. and Wang, Y. (2022). State Capacity in Historical Political Economy. *The Oxford Handbook of Historical Political Economy*, pp.C13.P1-C13.N8.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197618608.013.13>.
- Frankel, J.A. (2010). Mauritius: African Success Story. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. [online]
doi:<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1676286>.
- Galor, O. (2012). Inequality, Human Capital Formation and the Process of Development. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. [online] doi:<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2003661>.
- Sokoloff, K.L. and Engerman, S.L. (2000). History Lessons: Institutions, Factor Endowments, and Paths of Development in the New World. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 14(3), pp.217–232.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.14.3.217>.
- The Oxford Handbook of Historical Political Economy. (2022). *Oxford University Press eBooks*.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197618608.001.0001>.
- www.oecd-ilibrary.org. (2021). *Home*. [online] Available at: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/8806ab3b-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/8806ab3b-en>.

Yao, J., El-Masry, G., Khandelwal, P. and Sacerdoti, E. (2005). *Mauritius*. International Monetary Fund.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.5089/9781589064164.058>.